

SEAWATER DESALINATION

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Introduction

Over the past century, the consumption of fresh water in the world has increased by several times, and the Earth's water resources do not meet such a rapid increase in human needs, caused by an exponential population growth, expanding industry and a climate change, particularly droughts.

At present, over 2.8 billion of people around the world are coming up against water scarcity (Mohammadi et al., 2019). In 2021, the mean of irrevocable water consumption (i.e., a non-renewable water that cannot be replenished) in agriculture varied between 60%-80%, in industry 5%-15%, and in domestic sector 10%-15%. The amount of non-renewable water prevails in regions with a lack of water resources (Koronkevich, Barabanova and Zaitseva, 2022). In 2021 the total amount of water consumption was 4489 km³, 2247 km³ of this amount was a non-renewable water (Koronkevich, Barabanova and Zaitseva, 2022, fig. 4). Obtaining freshwater includes such techniques as wastewater treatment, atmospheric water collection, and seawater desalination (SD) (Cai et al., 2023). In 2019, the total amount of desalinated water production was 92.5 million m³ (0.0925 km³) daily (Mohammadi et al., 2019). This Report aims to give a brief description of main seawater desalination techniques, emphasizing their features and potential problems.

Methods

There are more than twenty methods of SD(Fig.1), however, in general, SD can be divided into membrane-based desalination (MBD), thermal distillation (TD) and solar steam generation (SSG) (Liu et al., 2022; Srishti et al., 2022; Cai et al., 2023).

Figure 1

Modified from source: (Cai et al., 2023, p. 2), Fig. 1. Various seawater desalination technologies and their corresponding materials. Image reproduced with permission of copyright., 'Advances in desalination technology and its environmental and economic assessment', *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 397, p. 136498., viewed 24 April 2023, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2023.136498>

Thermal distillation

TD consists of three similar methods, which differ in execution.

Low temperature multi-effect distillation (LT-MED) method is based on a seawater numerous evaporation and condensation in interconnected multiple tanks, with further pressure and temperature decrease in each subsequent tank (Fig 2a).

Figure 2a

Modified from source: (Cai *et al.*, 2023, p. 3), Fig. 2. Thermal distillation seawater desalination device: a) low temperature multi-effect distillation., 'Advances in desalination technology and its environmental and economic assessment', *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 397, p. 136498., viewed 24 April 2023, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2023.136498>

At each stage there is a continuous process of seawater separation into condensate, steam, brine and distillate water (Cai *et al.*, 2023, fig. 2a). A multi-stage flash (MSF) differs in that the seawater gets heated in a flash chamber to evaporate (Fig. 2b), instead of tanks, and operates at a higher temperature (Cai *et al.*, 2023, fig. 2b).

Figure 2b

Modified from source: (Cai *et al.*, 2023, p. 3), Fig. 2. Thermal distillation seawater desalination device: b) multi-stage flash evaporation., ‘Advances in desalination technology and its environmental and economic assessment’, *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 397, p. 136498., viewed 24 April 2023, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2023.136498>

A single vapor compression unit (VC)

Figure 2c

Modified from source: (Cai *et al.*, 2023, p. 3), Fig. 2. Thermal distillation seawater desalination device: c) vapor compression., ‘Advances in desalination technology and its environmental and economic assessment’, *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 397, p. 136498., viewed 24 April 2023, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2023.136498>

is a similar system; however, it operates at a lower level of pressure and temperature and does not require an external source of steam (Fig 2c), (Cai *et al.*, 2023, fig. 2c).

SSG(Fig.3)

Figure 3

Modified from source: (Cai *et al.*, 2023, p. 4), Fig. 5. Schematic of interface solar steam evaporation principle. Solar energy is transformed into heat energy through photothermal materials, from which the seawater is heated for evaporation and then condensed into freshwater through the evaporator. 'Advances in desalination technology and its environmental and economic assessment', *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 397, p. 136498., viewed 24 April 2023, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2023.136498>

There are three main categories of Solar evaporators (Fig.5): bottom heating evaporators, volume heating evaporators, and interface solar steam generation evaporators (ISSG), (Cai *et al.*, 2023, fig. 5). In a bottom heating system, a heat created at the receiver gets transferred to the water mass. The downside of this method is an inevitable heat loss and a low solar energy conversion efficiency, i.e., because of uneven heating (affecting only the bottom of reservoir by way of solar absorbers, made of photo-thermal material) only a small amount of solar energy will be transferred into the heat. When a volume heating system is in use, solar absorbers are scattered in a reservoir, and thus the heat gets distributed uniformly through the water mass. An efficiency of this approach remains questionable, since there is a significant loss of energy because of conduction (a heat transfer in environ) and convection (a collision of molecules of liquid or gas) (Liu *et al.*, 2022, fig. 3) and also the fact that absorber dispersed in reservoir

water mass has a low sensitivity to a heat. (Srishti et al., 2022). Also, Solar energy reflection and scattering among with radiation inevitably increase the heat loss.

Figure 4

Modified from source: (Liu *et al.*, 2022, fig. 3), *Fig. 3 Energy distribution of an interfacial water evaporation system.*, 'Advances and challenges of broadband solar absorbers for efficient solar steam generation', *ENVIRONMENTAL SCIENCE-NANO* [Preprint], viewed 24 April 2023, <https://doi.org/10.1039/d2en00070a>

ISSG evaporation technology (Fig.4) is the most efficient one, comparing with bottom heating and volume heating evaporation. The main advantage of this method is an application of a photo-thermal absorber above the water mass surface in a reservoir, where absorber is not in contact with the water, so the energy loss caused by conduction can be significantly reduced, since air is less conductive (Liu *et al.*, 2022). The energy loss caused by convection also gets decreased, because an absorber gets cooled down by an intensive water evaporation. The difference between isolated and non-isolated ISSG systems is that in an isolated system there is a certain kind of a thermal insulation, e.g., a constructed water channel, or a sponge (because of its porous structure, which would let the steam through).

Figure 5

Modified from source: (Liu *et al.*, 2022, fig. 4), Fig. 4 Categories of solar-driven evaporation systems. (a) Volumetric heating system: solar light is absorbed by uniformly dispersed solar absorbers and transformed into thermal energy to heat the bulk water. (b) Bottom heating system: bulk water is heated by thermal energy converted from solar light via solar absorbers on the bottom. (c) Interfacial heating system: the solar absorber floating on the water surface performs solar-to-thermal conversion at the air–water interface and in situ heats the surface water. (d) Isolation heating systems: (i) the solar absorber is separated from bulk water and water is transferred through specific channels; (ii) 3D-structured evaporator with enhanced environmental energy., ‘Advances and challenges of broadband solar absorbers for efficient solar steam generation’, *ENVIRONMENTAL SCIENCE-NANO* [Preprint], viewed 24 April 2023, <https://doi.org/10.1039/d2en00070a>

Exactly this ISSG option is considered more efficient, since the thermal insulation allows to achieve best results in preventing energy loss, by heating up uniformly, being in its own way an “adapter” between the water surface and the solar energy absorber, minimizing the impact of conduction and convection (Liu *et al.*, 2022; Srishti *et al.*, 2022, fig. 1B). As a result, the energy conversion efficiency can exceed 100 % (Liu *et al.*, 2022). Solar absorbers consist of photothermal materials and/or semiconductors, that, in turn, can include plasmonic materials (metals and metal-like materials, and/or composites of ceramics, carbide, and/or materials that enhance plasmonic effect (a resonance, that occurs as a result of interaction between

sunlight and metal nano-particles, that cause an oscillation of free electrons at a specific wavelengths of the sunlight) e.g., titanium dioxide, metals such as gold, silver, zinc, cuprum, et al., and carbonaceous materials). For example, a chemical element boron (B) has been used successfully in absorber manufacturing, since its spectral absorption range matches the spectral range of sunlight along with an ability to form stable molecular networks. (Pedro Alexandre Vieira Fernandes, 2014; Liu *et al.*, 2022; Srishti *et al.*, 2022; Cai *et al.*, 2023).

Membrane-based desalination (MBD)

The main MBD methods are as follows: membrane distillation (MD), electrodialysis (ED), forward osmosis (FO) and reverse osmosis (RO). All these methods have one common element - a semi-permeable membrane, which is a filter for a seawater. Membrane material and its features depend on the MBD method, also it is ultrathin, and the size of its pores is measured in nanometres (Cai *et al.*, 2023). There are several types of MD, but the basic principle of this method is the evaporation of water in a separated module through the Membrane (Fig 6), that forms a distillate (permeate).

Fig. 1. Direct-contact membrane distillation.

Fig. 2. Gas-gap membrane distillation.

Figure 6

Modified from source: (Smolders and Franken, 1989, p. 251), *Fig. 1. Direct-contact membrane distillation; Fig. 2. Gas-gap membrane distillation.*, ‘Terminology for Membrane Distillation’, *Desalination*, 72(3), pp. 249–262., viewed 24 April 2023, [https://doi.org/10.1016/0011-9164\(89\)80010-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/0011-9164(89)80010-4)

The difference of the temperature between the solution and the distillate (the distillate temperature is lower) in the evaporation system creates a pressure, which boosts MD process. To transfer distillate vapours outside of a membrane module a sweeping gas can be used (e.g., nitrogen) (Smolders and Franken, 1989). MD technology is widely applied in wastewater treatment. Electrodialysis (Fig.7) occurs in a tank separated by two membranes, one of which passes negatively charged ions (anions), and the other one - positively charged.

Figure 7

Modified from source: (Al-Amshawee *et al.*, 2020, p. 11), Fig. 8. Scheme of reverse electrodialysis process (adapted from ref. [40])., 'Electrodialysis desalination for water and wastewater: A review', *Chemical Engineering Journal*, 380, p. 122231., viewed 24 April 2023, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cej.2019.122231>

In this case, the liquid enters the intermediate compartments separated by membranes (one tank can have more than two compartments), and the salt remains in the bath (Al-Amshawee *et al.*, 2020). FO (Fig.8) is based on a natural physical process when a less concentrated solution tends to a more concentrated one, in this case, a seawater flows through the

membrane from one compartment to another one,

Fig. 2. Schematic diagram of the novel ammonia-carbon dioxide forward osmosis desalination process.

Figure 8

Modified from source: (McCutcheon, McGinnis and Elimelech, 2005, p. 5), *Fig. 2. Schematic diagram of the novel ammonia-carbon dioxide forward osmosis desalination process.*, 'A novel ammonia—carbon dioxide forward (direct) osmosis desalination process', *Desalination*, 174(1), pp. 1–11., viewed 24 April 2023, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.desal.2004.11.002>

e.g., that contains a concentrated ammonium bicarbonate solution, thus salt and other impurities remain in the first compartment, and at the time of medium heating (approx. 60°C), ammonium bicarbonate can be broken down into ammonia and carbon dioxide gases, and the gases can be later released by a distillation under low temperature, minimizing the energy consumption (McCutcheon, McGinnis and Elimelech, 2005).

RO occurs in the opposite direction (Fig.9).

Figure 9

Modified from source: (Lu, Liao and Hu, 2012, p. 44), Fig 1. The schematic diagram of a RO unit., ‘The design of reverse osmosis systems with multiple-feed and multiple-product’, *Desalination*, 307, pp. 42–50., viewed 24 April 2023, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.desal.2012.08.025>

It is impossible to achieve this naturally — therefore, water gets pumped through the membrane under a certain pressure, which should exceed the osmotic pressure (Lu, Liao and Hu, 2012).

In addition to this, another innovative method must be mentioned: as is known, mangrove

Figure 10

Modified from source: (Wang et al., 2020, p. 2), Fig. 1. Design elements and water flow in the synthetic mangrove., ‘Capillary-driven desalination in a synthetic mangrove’, *Science Advances*, 6(8), viewed 24 April 2022, <https://doi.org/10.1126/sciadv.aax5253>

trees (Fig.10) can filter salty water by means of generated negative pressure in mangrove leaves, so, a synthetic mangrove is now under development (Wang *et al.*, 2020).

Potential problems

Problems of applying SD techniques are as follows: complexity of equipment and/or preparation (MSF,RO,FO,ED), large investment (ISSG, MSF), low efficiency (LT-MED,VC).

Along with that, implementing SD techniques depend on natural factors of a geographical region, salinity of water, labour cost, environmental management and sometimes even territorial disputes. Currently, freshwater comes by mostly through RO, LT-MED and MSF, but RO is a leader among SD techniques due to consolidation of efficiency and low production cost (Cai *et al.*, 2023; Walschot and Katz, 2022).

Generally, SD faces three main issues: a high energy cost, the price of which often overrides the benefits from obtaining permeate, significant impairment of environment, resulting in destruction of marine life, especially fish and fish eggs that enter an SD plant pipe intake and brine discharge remaining after water purification, which contains hazardous chemical compounds, and legal challenges, arising from a conflict of regulations of environmental bodies, that maintain SD plant operating area (a coastal zone, which can be densely populated, which in turn creates additional legal hurdles). These factors resulted in that, e.g., some municipalities of California plan to refuse from SD, while on the other hand up to 35% of all drinking water in Israel gets obtained by desalination (Denson, 2015), due to its geographic features and the political situation in the region.

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